

PREDICTION OF COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF PLAIN WEAVE FABRIC COMPOSITES

Kumar Rajesh S. and N. K. Naik
Aerospace Engineering Department
Indian Institute of Technology
Bombay 400 076, India

ABSTRACT

An analytical model for prediction of compressive strength of two dimensional orthogonal plain weave fabric composites is presented in this paper. The model is based on the curved beam/arch analysis and allows for different laminate configurations and the secondary failure modes in the failure strength prediction.

INTRODUCTION

The increasing usage of fiber reinforced polymer composites in primary structural application demands a better understanding of these materials. The determination of compressive strength is of considerable importance as these materials are generally weak in compression and thus fail as a result of damage initiation due to compressive stresses. However, this area is still the least understood field in composites today. This is because of the various parameters which affect the compressive behavior as well as the difficulty in determining the true compressive strength experimentally. In fiber reinforced polymer composites, compression failure may be defined as the failure of the material without specimen buckling or any other global defects triggering the failure mechanism. The inherent waviness as in textile composites or fiber waviness in unidirectional (UD) composites are considered as a part of the material system.

Compression failure in UD composites is now understood to be due to microbuckling and kinking mechanisms. Microbuckling of fibers usually initiates the failure process resulting in a kink band formation in the post buckling regime. Due to the random nature of defects in the form of waviness in these materials considerable empiricism is present in most of the analytical models [1,2]. A good review on all the aspects of UD composite compression behavior is given by Camponeschi [3].

Woven Fabric (WF) composites owing to their high damage tolerance and impact resistance are increasingly used either alone or in unison with UD composites in primary structural components. The thermoelastic properties [4] and failure behavior of WF composites under

tensile and in-plane shear loading [5,6] have been evaluated. However, the behavior of WF composites under compressive loading is not studied to the same extent. Literature shows a highly simplified model by Wilkinson et al [7]. Other works are qualitative in nature, for example, Karayaka and Kurath [8] and Cox et al [9] have discussed the modes of failure in 2D and 3D woven composites respectively. Reifsnider and Mirjadeh [10] have conducted experimental investigations on the compression behavior of notched and unnotched satin weave fabric laminates.

In this scenario, the understanding of compressive behavior and the compressive strength prediction of WF composites is very essential to achieve a high level of confidence in their application.

ANALYTICAL MODEL

An analytical model developed for the prediction of compressive strength of 2D orthogonal plain weave fabric laminates is presented below.

WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITE GEOMETRY

Woven fabric composites consist of woven fabric preforms embedded in a suitable matrix. Fabrics may be of different types depending on the weaving pattern. In the present formulation only orthogonal plain weave fabric composite is considered. This consists of two strand systems in perpendicular direction referred to as fill and warp strands. The strands are woven in a regular sequence of one over and one under. A general geometrical representative unit cell is shown in Fig. 1. In this a , g , h represent the strand width, inter-strand gap and thickness of the strand respectively. The subscripts w and f indicate warp and fill direction respectively. Three idealized configurations are possible in WF laminates [6]. These are named as C1, C2 and C3 laminate configurations. In C1 configuration the laminae are exactly one over the other without any in-plane shift. If two identical unit cells as shown in Fig.1 are placed one over the other, the resulting configuration would be C1. However, if the upper unit cell is placed over the lower, the resulting laminate would be C2. In this the interlacing region of one layer bridges the gap region of the adjacent layer. In C3 configuration, there is through the thickness shift along with the in-plane shifts. In actual practice, the occurrence of configuration C2 during lamination is more probable [6].

FAILURE MECHANISM

Under in-plane compressive loading, the stresses are generated in all the three constituents of the material, namely, warp strand, fill strand and the matrix region. If the loading is considered to be along the warp strand, the maximum load is taken by this strand and the remaining by the fill and matrix because of the difference in their stiffness in loading direction. As the load is gradually increased, the failure is likely to initiate in the matrix region or in the fill strand due to their low strength. This would cause an increase in the warp strand stress. The ultimate failure of the laminate would take place by the failure of the warp strand. Different possible primary failure modes are: shear failure of the warp strand, transverse failure of the warp strand and failure of the warp strand due to combined normal and bending stresses. The secondary modes are: bond separation between warp and fill strand, failure of the fill strand and failure in the pure matrix region. These failure modes are shown schematically in Fig. 2.

MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

The applied compressive load in a WF composite causes the load bearing strand (warp strand) to bend from its initially curved shape. The bending is resisted by the matrix and the fill strand. The analysis is for symmetric laminates thus ignores the coupling stiffness. The warp strand is modeled as a curved beam/arch. The effect of the fill strand, the matrix region and the adjacent layer is modeled as a reaction to the warp strand. The analysis is similar to Hetenyi's analysis [11] for an arch on elastic foundation except that the matrix, fill and adjacent layer restraint is modeled by lumping them in the form of linear springs. The governing equation is obtained by considering a differential element of the strand as shown in Fig. 3. This element is acted upon by normal force, N , shear force, Q and bending moment, M . The resulting differential equation for bending of the strand is obtained from the force and moment equilibrium as:

$$\frac{d^5 y}{d\varphi^5} + 2 \frac{d^3 y}{d\varphi^3} + \frac{dy}{d\varphi} = 0 \tag{1}$$

The general solution of this differential equation is:

$$y = c_0 + (c_1 + c_2\varphi) \cos\varphi + (c_3 + c_4\varphi) \sin\varphi \tag{2}$$

The constants $c_i, i = 0,4$ are determined from the boundary conditions of the problem. Using this expression, the moment, shear force, and normal force are obtained in terms of the unknown constants as:

$$M = \frac{-E_{11}^s I_s}{r^2} (c_0 - 2c_2 \sin\varphi + 2c_4 \cos\varphi) \tag{3}$$

$$Q = \frac{2E_{11}^s I_s}{r^3} (c_2 \cos\varphi + c_4 \sin\varphi) \tag{4}$$

$$N = \frac{2E_{11}^s I_s}{r^3} (c_2 \sin\varphi - c_4 \cos\varphi) \tag{5}$$

where E_{11}^s and I_s denote the strand elastic modulus and second moment of area respectively. φ is defined as shown in Fig. 3 and r is the radius of the differential element. The angular deflection θ due to bending is obtained by integrating $M / (E_{11}^s I_s)$ along the strand:

$$\theta = \frac{-1}{r} [c_0 \varphi + 2c_2 (\cos\varphi - 1) + 2c_4 \sin\varphi] \tag{6}$$

The horizontal displacement due to bending at any point on the strand can be obtained using the above expression in the following equation:

$$u_b = - \int_0^\varphi \theta r \sin\varphi d\varphi \tag{7}$$

giving

$$u_b = c_0 (\sin\varphi - \varphi \cos\varphi) + c_2 (2 \cos\varphi - 0.5 \cos 2\varphi - 1.5) + c_4 (\varphi - 0.5 \sin 2\varphi) \tag{8}$$

The total horizontal displacement, u is the sum of the displacement due to bending and that due to axial deformation. The expression for the horizontal displacement due to the axial force, u_a is given by:

$$u_a = \frac{P}{A_w} (r \sin\varphi) \left[\frac{1}{E_{11}^s} \cos^2 \varphi + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}^s} - \frac{2\nu_{12}^s}{E_{11}^s} \right) \sin^2 \varphi \cos^2 \varphi + \frac{1}{E_{22}^s} \sin^2 \varphi \right] \tag{9}$$

Figure 1. A general plain weave fabric lamina geometrical representative unit cell.

Figure 2. Possible failure modes in WF composites under compression.

Figure 3. Modeling of plain weave fabric lamina geometrical representative unit cell.

where P is the applied force, A_w is the warp cross sectional area and G_{12}^s and ν_{12}^s represent the shear modulus and Poisson's ratio of the warp strand. The vertical displacement, v is related to the horizontal displacement, u and radial displacement, y by the following relation:

$$v = \frac{y - u \sin \phi}{\cos \phi} \quad (10)$$

SOLUTION PROCEDURE

For the present problem, the unit cell is divided in to a number of slices with the slice perpendicular to the loading direction. The value of constants $c_0 - c_4$ remain same within one slice but differ from one slice to another. Thus the number of unknowns are 5 times the number of slices. Owing to symmetry of one unit cell and the loading, only a quarter unit cell is considered for the analysis. Assuming simply supported boundary condition in the gap region, conditions of symmetry at the other end and the compatibility conditions at the junction of two slices, simultaneous equations equal to the total number of unknowns are obtained. These are solved to obtain the values of unknown constants for each slice. From these values the moment, shear force, normal force, horizontal and vertical deflection at any point along the strand are obtained.

FAILURE ANALYSIS

The failure load and hence failure strength is determined by solving the system of equations, determining the maximum stress in the warp strand and equating it to the corresponding strand strength. The load is increased in increment till the warp strand fails in one of the primary failure modes. At each load level, the stresses in the other components of the slice namely, matrix and fill strand is determined from the load sharing. The load taken by the component is taken to be zero once it fails. In that case the entire load in the slice is taken by the warp strand. The lowest value of the compressive strength for different primary failure modes gives the compressive strength of the unit cell / WF laminate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analytical model presented in the above section is validated through an experimental program on E-glass/epoxy material system. The testing was carried out at room temperature using the Illinois Institute of Technology Research Institute (IITRI) fixture and method as described by ASTM D3410. Three material systems with differing fabric geometrical and weave parameters were used. These material systems are referred to as GLE1-GLE3. The geometrical parameters are described in Tables 1 and 2. Using the geometry of these material system and the strand properties as listed in Table 3, different failure modes using the proposed model are analyzed. The results from this study are given in Table 4. It is seen that the failure due to transverse stresses and bond separation between fill and warp strands are not likely to take place. Out of the two primary modes namely shear failure of the warp strand and failure due to combined normal and bending stresses, the shear failure in the gap region occurred at a lower applied stress and hence it is the critical mode for the material system considered. The comparison with experimental results is presented in Table 5. The analytical predictions are in close agreement with the experimental values.

A parametric study to elucidate the effect of fabric geometry on compressive strength is carried out using balanced T-300 carbon/epoxy material. The effect of two parameters, namely inter-strand gap to strand width ratio (g/a) and strand thickness to width ratio (h/a) is studied. The results are presented in Fig 4 and Fig. 5 respectively. It is seen that the compressive strength is a function of both these parameters. With increase in g/a the strength reduces due to increase in the pure matrix region and hence the reduction in the overall fiber volume fraction. With increase in h/a ratio, the strand curvature increases, thereby reducing the compressive strength.

Figure 4. Effect of g/a on compressive strength.

Figure 5. Effect of h/a on compressive strength.

Table 1. Strand and Fabric Properties

Material	Crimp, C (%)		No. of Counts (per cm)	
	Fill	Warp	Fill	Warp
E-Glass/Epoxy				
GLE1	0.22	0.22	14.1	14.1
GLE2	0.72	0.15	12.0	17.5
GLE3	0.30	0.27	7.0	6.6

Table 2. Fabric Geometrical Parameters ($h_f = h_w = h_t / 2$)

Material	Fabric Thickness, h_t (mm)	Fill Strand			Warp Strand		
		a_f (mm)	g_f (mm)	h_f (mm)	a_w (mm)	g_w (mm)	h_w (mm)
E-Glass/ Epoxy							
GLE1	0.086	0.50	0.21	0.043	0.51	0.21	0.043
GLE2	0.180	0.57	0.26	0.090	0.57	0.00	0.090
GLE3	0.200	1.23	0.20	0.100	1.13	0.39	0.100

Table 3. Elastic and Strength Properties of Strand / UD Lamina

Material ($V_f=0.7$)	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	X_T (MPa)	X_C (MPa)	Y_T (MPa)	Y_C (MPa)	S (MPa)
E-Glass / Epoxy T-300	51.4	17.5	5.8	0.31	1426	800	29.1	150	46
Carbon / Epoxy	162	14.8	5.6	0.28	1744	1500	52.6	150	108

Table 4. Analytical Strength Predictions for Different Failure Modes for Plain Weave Fabric Laminates (C2 Configuration)

Sr. No.	Failure Modes	Compressive Strength (MPa) for Material Systems		
		GLE1 $V_f^o = 0.28$	GLE2 $V_f^o = 0.34$	GLE3 $V_f^o = 0.35$
1.	Shear failure of the warp strand	213	200	202
2.	Failure of the warp strand due to combined normal and bending stresses	230	300	255
3.	Transverse failure of the warp strand	2938	1304	2331
4.	Bond separation between warp and fill strands	3695	1641	2932

Table 5. Predicted (For C2) and Experimental Compressive Strengths for Plain Weave Fabric Laminates (MPa)

Material (E-Glass/Epoxy)	Predicted	Experimental
GLE1	213	--
GLE2	200	213
GLE3	202	209

CONCLUSIONS

An analytical model based on curved beam /arch analysis is presented to predict the compressive strength of 2D orthogonal plain weave fabric laminates. The evaluation of different failure modes visualized for WF composites indicates that the shear failure of the warp strand or compression failure due to combined normal and bending stresses leads to the ultimate failure of the laminate. These failure modes are influenced by the secondary failure modes such as transverse failure of the fill strand and failure in the pure matrix region. The predicted values agree well with the experimental data for E-glass/epoxy laminates. The strength is sensitive to fabric geometry.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank the Structures Panel, Aeronautics Research and Development Board, Ministry of Defense, Government of India for sponsoring this project.

REFERENCES

1. K. H. Lo and E. S. M. Chim, Compressive strength of unidirectional composites. *J. Reinforced Plastics Comp.* 11, 838-896 (1992).
2. B. Budiansky and N. A. Fleck, Compressive failure of fiber composites. *J. Mech. Phys. Solids.* 41, 183-211 (1993).
3. E. T. Camponeschi, Jr., Compression of composite materials: A review. in *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Fracture (Third Volume)*, ASTM STP 1110, T. K. O'Brien, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 550-578 (1991).
4. N. K. Naik, *Woven Fabric Composites*. Technomic Publishing Co., Inc., Lancaster, PA (1994).
5. N. K. Naik and V. K. Ganesh, Failure Behavior of Plain Weave Fabric Laminates under on-axes Uniaxial Tensile Loading. Report No. IITB/AE/ARDB/STR/659/93/02, IIT, Bombay (1993).
6. N. K. Naik and V. K. Ganesh, Failure behavior of plain weave fabric laminates under in-plane shear loading. *J. Comp. Tech. Res.* 16, 3-20 (1994).
7. E. Wilkinson, T. V. Parry and A. S. Wronski, Compression failure in two types of carbon fiber-epoxide laminates. *Comp. Sci. Tech.* 26, 17-29 (1986).
8. M. Karayaka and P. Kurath, Deformation and failure behavior of woven composite laminates. *J. Engg. Mater. Tech., Trans. ASME* 116, 222-232 (1994)
9. B. N. Cox, M. S. Dadkhah, W. L. Morris and J. G. Flintoff, Failure mechanisms of 3D woven composites in tension, compression and bending. *Acta Metall. Mater.* 42, 3967-3984 (1994).
10. K. L. Reifsnider and F. Mirzadeh, Compressive strength and mode of failure of 8H Celion 3000/PMR15 woven composite material. *J. Comp. Tech. Res.* 10, 156-164 (1988).
11. M. Hetenyi, *Beams on Elastic Foundation*. The University of Michigan Press, Ann Arbor, Michigan (1961).